

Triphenylamine-based oxidized bis(indolyl)methane as fluorogenic and chromogenic chemosensor for anions

Kumaresh Ghosh^{*a} and Indrajit Saha^{a,b}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani-741 235, Nadia, West Bengal, India

E-mail : ghosh_k2003@yahoo.co.in

^bDepartment of Chemistry, R. K. Mahavidyalaya, Kailashahar, Unakoti-741 235, Tripura, India

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Abstract : Triphenylamine coupled oxidised bis(indolyl)methane **1** has been designed and synthesized for optical sensing of anions in organic (CH₃CN) and semi aqueous (CH₃CN/H₂O, 4 : 1, v/v) medium. The sensory system exhibited ratiometric change in emission upon addition of fluoride anion in CH₃CN. Further, the chemosensor **1** displayed selective coloration from yellow to pink in presence of F⁻ anion in CH₃CN while in aqueous acetonitrile sharp colour change from yellow to pink was observed upon addition of HSO₄⁻ only. The differential selectivity of **1** in different medium is attributed to the different proton transfer signaling modes.

Keywords : Bis(indolyl)methane, fluoride sensing, hydrogen sulphate sensing, ratiometric sensing, triphenylamine.

Introduction

The significant role that anions play in biological, environmental and medicinal science has inspired supramolecular chemists to design and synthesize numerous receptors for the recognition and sensing of anionic substrates¹. Owing to their diverse geometry, low charge to radii ratios, narrow pH window and high solvation energy, design of anion receptor that operate with high sensitivity and selectivity towards desired analytes is particularly difficult. Charge-charge interactions, hydrogen bonding interactions, coordination bonds and hydrophobic interactions are the key tools that have been widely utilized for the recognition and sensing of anionic species. As a result, numerous reports that take the advantages of metal ions², pyridinium³, imidazolium/benzimidazolium⁴, guanidinium⁵, polyammonium⁶, urea/thiourea⁷, amide⁸, pyrrole⁹ and calixpyrrole¹⁰ functionalities have been documented in literature. In this regard, synthetic receptors that signal the presence of anions through change in luminescence as well as colour of the solu-

tion have drawn significant attention in recent years¹¹.

Among the various anions, fluoride has received special attention due to its potential toxicity in various living systems. Scientific challenges along with societal issues associated with the smallest anion fluoride have made the recognition and sensing of this anion by synthetic hosts is of special interest¹². For example, low concentration of fluoride in human diet has beneficial health effects, particularly in dental care. However, excess consumption of fluoride has toxic side effects, related to various human pathologies such as neurological dysfunction, osteosarcoma etc. Although significant progress has been made in the field of fluoride recognition and sensing, there are only a few easy-to-use chemosensors that operate with high sensitivity owing to its high charge density and high hydration energy.

The oxidised bis(indolyl)methane is a well established chromophoric unit that recognizes anions in both organic and aqueous organic solvents by exhibiting color change of the solution. It provides an acidic hy-

drogen bond donor moiety and a basic hydrogen-bond acceptor moiety for anion binding. Shao and co-workers first reported that the oxidised bis(indolyl)methane is an efficient chromogenic-sensing system for anion¹³. This colorimetric anion sensor exhibited selective coloration either for F^- in aprotic solvent or for HSO_4^- in water containing medium based on different proton transfer signaling modes. The same group modified the bis(indolyl)methane system to tris(indolyl)methene, a new kind of unexplored chromogenic molecules¹⁴. These molecules can act as excellent chemosensors for F^- by two stages of proton transfer along with stepwise drastic colour changes, and could also distinguish AcO^- and $H_2PO_4^-$ through spectral behaviours. Kim *et al.* also designed and synthesized dual colorimetric sensing system based on this bis-(indolyl)methane skeleton¹⁵.

Herein, we intended to study the anion binding behavior of the oxidised bis(indolyl)methane when it remains attached to the triphenylamine unit. The propeller-shaped triphenylamine platform serves as an ex-

cellent fluorescent probe and has been extensively used by us and other groups in molecular recognition studies¹⁶. In the design **1**, triphenyl-amine acts as fluorophore as well as electron donor group and conjugated bis(indolyl) skeleton acts as a potential chromophoric unit which contains an acidic hydrogen bond donor and a basic hydrogen bond acceptor.

Results and discussion

The synthesis of the designed compound **1** was achieved according to the Scheme 1. It starts with 4-(diphenylamino)benzaldehyde **2** which was synthesized using literature procedure^{16d}. The condensation reaction of **2** with indole in CH_3OH afforded the compound **3** in 90% yields. The subsequent oxidation of **3** with DDQ in CH_3CN gave the desired compound **1** in 37% yields. All the compounds were characterized using 1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR, FTIR, and Mass spectroscopic tools.

The anion binding properties of **1** were investigated using fluorescence, UV-Vis, and 1H NMR spectroscopic techniques. The receptor **1** exhibited a well defined fluorescence band with maxima at 365 nm and 512 nm upon excitation at 300 nm in CH_3CN . The bands at 365 nm and 512 nm were assigned to triphenylamine and bis(3-indolyl)methane moieties, respectively. Upon complexation with the anions, the emission intensities of both the bands were perturbed differently depending upon the anionic species (Fig. 1). While the emission intensity at 365 nm was found to be enhanced greatly upon complexation of $H_2PO_4^-$,

Scheme 1. Reagents and conditions : (i) $KHSO_4$, dry CH_3OH , rt, 4 h, 90%; (ii) DDQ, dry CH_3CN , 4 h, 37%.

Fig. 1. Change in emission of receptor **1** ($c = 3.55 \times 10^{-5} M$) upon addition of 15 equivalent amounts of putative anions in CH_3CN .

the peak at ~ 512 nm was changed merely (Fig. 2). Among the halides, only F^- ion interacted with **1** significantly. The change in emission of **1** with the increase in concentration of F^- ion is different from the other anions examined in the present study (Fig. 1).

Fig. 2. Change in emission of receptor **1** ($c = 3.55 \times 10^{-5} M$) upon addition of H_2PO_4^- in CH_3CN .

Fig. 3 demonstrates that the titration of **1** with F^- follows a ratiometric change in emission with an

Fig. 3. Change in emission of receptor **1** ($c = 3.55 \times 10^{-5} M$) upon addition of F^- in CH_3CN .

isobestic point at 468 nm. With the increase in concentration of F^- , while the intensity of the peak at 365 nm was increased, the emission at 512 nm was decreased gradually. Such characteristic spectral change was observed only with F^- and is thus diagnostic to differentiate F^- fluorimetrically from other anions taken in the study. It is worthy to note that ratiometric fluorescent probes have the important feature in that they permit signal rationing increase the dynamic range and provide bait-in correction for environmental effects¹⁷. Other anions such as Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- , CH_3COO^- , ClO_4^- and HSO_4^- interacted very weakly in CH_3CN showing no significant change in emission of **1**.

In aqueous CH_3CN ($\text{CH}_3\text{CN} : \text{H}_2\text{O}$, 4 : 1, v/v), the receptor **1** showed only one emission band at 372 nm upon excitation at 300 nm. However, no significant change in emission intensity of this band was observed upon addition of various anions. Fig. 4, in this aspect, represents the change in emission of **1** upon addition of 15 equivalent amounts of anions in aqueous CH_3CN .

The ground state interaction of **1** with the anions was investigated through UV-Vis spectroscopic technique in both CH_3CN and aqueous CH_3CN ($\text{CH}_3\text{CN} :$

Fig. 4. Change in emission of receptor **1** ($c = 3.55 \times 10^{-5} M$) upon addition of 15 equivalent amounts of putative anions in CH₃CN/H₂O (4 : 1, v/v).

Fig. 5. Change in absorbance of receptor **1** ($c = 3.55 \times 10^{-5} M$) upon addition of 15 equivalent amounts of putative anions in CH₃CN.

H₂O, 4 : 1, v/v) solvents. The receptor **1** showed two absorption bands at 284 nm and 436 nm along with a weak shouldering at around 550 nm in CH₃CN. The strong absorption band at 436 nm, responsible for yellow colour of the solution, was assigned as the ICT absorption band of the conjugated bis(indole) skeleton. The less strong shoulder peak at 550 nm is related to its intermolecular hydrogen bond interaction, which disappeared upon addition of polar protic solvent such as H₂O and CH₃OH¹².

Fig. 5 collectively represents the change in absorption of **1** upon addition of various anions. Except fluoride, other anions did not show any red or blue shift in the absorption spectra. Fig. 6 illustrates the change in absorption of **1** with increase in concentration of F⁻ in CH₃CN. As the concentration of F⁻ ion increases, absorbance at 436 nm decreases with a blue shift of 35 nm and a new band at 520 nm appeared showing an isosbestic point at 480 nm. Three other isosbestic points were noticed at 246 nm, 310 nm and 366 nm. In the event the colour of the solution changes from yellow to pink and this is attributed to the formation of deprotonated receptor (Fig. 7A). Initially, F⁻ ion forms hydrogen bonding complex and at high concentration,

Fig. 6. Change in absorbance of receptor **1** ($c = 3.55 \times 10^{-5} M$) upon addition of F⁻ in CH₃CN.

by virtue of its basic nature, it deprotonates the receptor. The new band at 520 nm was related to the formation of deprotonated receptor. Such deprotonation was related to the acidity of the H-bond donor sites and the particular stability of [HF₂]⁻ hydrogen bond complex¹⁸.

On the other hand, in aqueous CH₃CN (CH₃CN : H₂O, 4 : 1, v/v), the compound **1** behaved differently towards the same anions. In this solvent composition,

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Fig. 7. Change in colour of **1** ($c = 5.00 \times 10^{-5} M$) upon addition of 10 equivalent amounts various anions in (A) CH_3CN and (B) $\text{CH}_3\text{CN} : \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (4 : 1, v/v) : (a) **1**, (b) ClO_4^- , (c) H_2PO_4^- , (d) CH_3COO^- , (e) HSO_4^- , (f) NO_3^- , (g) F^- , (h) Cl^- , (i) Br^- , (j) I^- .

no characteristic change in UV-Vis spectra of **1**, upon titration with various anions, was observed except for HSO_4^- and CH_3COO^- .

Fig. 8 represents the change in absorbance with increase in concentration of F^- , CH_3COO^- and HSO_4^- . During complexation of AcO^- , the band at 455 nm moved to 478 nm with the appearance of a weak shoulder peak at 540 nm (Fig. 8b). In the case of HSO_4^- , the band at 455 nm underwent red shift showing new absorption band at 528 nm, which was gradually intensified upon complexation (Fig. 8c). This resulted in a visual color change from yellow to pink (Fig. 7B). Since the HSO_4^- anion is a relatively strong acid ($\text{p}K_a = 1.99$ in aqueous solution), the HSO_4^- -induced change is mainly the consequence of a simple protonation of receptor **1**. The band that develops at 500 nm pertains to the protonated receptor $[\text{H}_2\text{1}]^+$, which was confirmed by the protonation of receptor **1** by using perchloric/acetic acid in $\text{CH}_3\text{CN}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or in CH_3CN ¹³.

The interaction of **1** with F^- was also probed using ¹H NMR experiments, carried out in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ (solubility problems in CD_3CN in ¹H NMR concentration range prevented the study in CD_3CN). The signals for NH- proton in **1** was difficult to identify. This may be either due to significant broadening or overlapping with the other signals appeared in the aromatic region. However, it was found that the signals for indole ring protons in **1** underwent upfield shift upon addition of 0–2 equivalent amounts of F^- ion (Fig. 9). These observations reveal that F^- first establishes H-bond interaction with the NH subunit of **1**, while the second F^- induces the deprotonation of the NH fragment, which brings electron density onto the π -conjugated framework with through-bond propagation, thus causing a shielding effect and inducing upfield shift. In the full deprotonated form, the polarization effect is no longer present since the anion does not remain in proximity to the receptor.

Fig. 8. Change in absorbance of receptor **1** ($c = 3.55 \times 10^{-5} M$) upon addition : (a) F⁻, (b) AcO⁻, (c) HSO₄⁻ in CH₃CN/H₂O (4 : 1, v/v).

Conclusion

In conclusion, it has been shown that triphenylamine coupled oxidized bis(indolyl)methane **1** can report the selective recognition of anions through the change in photophysical properties of the triphenylamine unit. The compound works both in organic and aqueous organic solvents. The ratiometric change in emission, observed only with F⁻ in CH₃CN, is diagnostic to differentiate F⁻ anion fluorimetrically from other anions taken in the study. Also, the sensor exhibited selective coloration either for F⁻ in aprotic solvent and or for HSO₄⁻ in water containing medium based on different proton transfer signaling modes. The change in color of the receptor solution upon complexation of F⁻ and HSO₄⁻ is sharp and reproducible. Further work

along this direction is underway in the laboratory.

Experimental

General : Reagents and solvents were purified using standard techniques. Solvents were dried over the appropriate drying agent following standard procedure. Solvents for spectroscopic measurements were of spectroscopic or HPLC grade. Infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer L120-00A spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded at 400 MHz using Bruker instrument. Mass spectra were recorded on API 2000 LCMS/MS instrument. Fluorescence measurements were done using Perkin-Elmer LS55 and UV-Vis absorption spectra were recorded at room temperature using Perkin-Elmer Lambda 25.

Fig. 9. Partial ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$, 400 MHz) spectra of **1** ($8.20 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$) in the presence and absence of F^- ion.

4-(Di(1*H*-indol-3-yl)methyl)-*N,N*-diphenylaniline **3**

KHSO_4 (0.170 g, 1.25 mmol) was added to a mixture of indole (0.292 g, 2.5 mmol) and the aldehyde **2** (0.342 g, 1.25 mmol) in dry methanol (10 mL), and the reaction was stirred at room temperature for 4 h. Then water (10 mL) was added to quench the reaction, and the aqueous phase was extracted with CH_2Cl_2 ($3 \times 10 \text{ mL}$). The organic phase was dried with anhydrous Na_2SO_4 , and was removed under reduced pressure to give the crude product. Repeated crystallization of the crude product using the mixture solvent (ethyl acetate : petroleum ether = 1 : 3, v/v) afforded the product **3** as white solid (0.445 g, yield 90%), m.p. $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (decomposed); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.93 (2H, s), 7.43 (2H, d, $J=8 \text{ Hz}$), 7.36 (2H, d, $J=8 \text{ Hz}$), 7.23–7.15 (8H, m), 7.08–6.94 (10H, m), 6.72 (2H, s), 5.84 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : 147.9, 145.7, 138.5, 136.7, 129.4, 129.1, 127.1, 125.6, 124.1, 123.9, 123.5, 122.4, 121.9, 119.9, 119.8, 119.2, 111.0; FTIR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3417, 3057, 3035, 1587, 1505, 1493.

Receptor **1**

To a stirred solution of **3** (0.244 g, 0.5 mmol) in CH_3CN (10 mL), DDQ (0.068 g, 0.3 mmol) dissolved in CH_3CN (5 mL) was slowly added. The reaction

mixture was further stirred for 4 h, gave a dark red precipitate, which was filtered, washed with CH_3CN , and recrystallized from ethanol to afford pure compound **1** (0.100 g, yield 37%), m.p. $140 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (decomposed); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) : δ 7.96 (2H, s), 7.54 (2H, d, $J=8 \text{ Hz}$), 7.41 (4H, t, $J=8 \text{ Hz}$), 7.33 (2H, d, $J=8 \text{ Hz}$), 7.22–7.15 (8H, m), 7.00 (4H, d, $J=8 \text{ Hz}$), 6.85 (2H, d, $J=8 \text{ Hz}$); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) : δ 151.8, 149.7, 146.2, 133.4, 131.9, 129.8, 129.3, 128.1, 125.4, 124.5, 124.3, 123.2, 122.2, 120.8, 119.9, 116.1 (one carbon in aromatic region is unresolved); FTIR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3392, 3063, 1608, 1588, 1556, 1529, 1503, 1489; MS (LCMS) $\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{25}\text{N}_3$ requires 487.20; found 488.4 ($\text{M}+\text{H}$) $^+$.

General procedures of UV-Vis and fluorescence titration

Stock solutions of the hosts and guests were prepared in CH_3CN or $\text{CH}_3\text{CN-H}_2\text{O}$ and 2.5 ml of the individual host solution was taken in the cuvette. The solution was irradiated at the excitation wavelength maintaining the excitation and emission slits. Upon addition of guest anions, the change in fluorescence emission of the host was noticed. The corresponding emission values during titration were noted. For UV-Vis titration the receptors were dissolved in dry UV

grade CH₃CN or CH₃CN-H₂O and 2.5 ml of the individual host solution was taken in the cuvette. Then, anions, dissolved in dry CH₃CN were individually added in different amounts to the receptor solution and the corresponding absorbance values during titration were noted.

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References

- (a) P. A. Gale and C. Caltagirone, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2015, **44**, 4212; (b) N. Busschaert, C. Caltagirone, W. Van Rossom and P. A. Gale, *Chem. Rev.*, 2015, **115**, 8038; (c) J. Seesler, P. A. Gale and W.-S. Cho, "Anion Receptor Chemistry", Royal Society of Chemistry, Cambridge, 2006; (d) A. Bianchi, K. Bowman-James and E. García España, "Supramolecular Chemistry of Anions", Wiley VCH, New York, 1997.
- (a) J. P. Leonard, C. M. G. dos Santos, S. E. Plush, T. McCabe and T. Gunnlaugsson, *Chem. Commun.*, 2007, 129; (b) S. E. Plush and T. Gunnlaugson, *Org. Lett.*, 2007, **9**, 1919; (c) I. Carreira-Barral, T. Rodriguez-Blas, C. Platas-Iglesias, A. de Blas and D. Esteban-Gomez, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2014, **53**, 2554.
- K. Ghosh, A. R. Sarkar, T. Sarkar, S. Panja and D. Kar, *RSC Adv.*, 2014, **4**, 20114.
- (a) J. Yoon, S. K. Kim, N. J. Singh and K. S. Kim, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2006, **35**, 355; (b) Z. C. Xu, S. K. Kim and J. Yoon, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2010, **39**, 1457; (c) K. Ghosh and D. Kar, *Beilstein J. Org. Chem.*, 2011, **7**, 254; (d) K. Ghosh, I. Saha, R. Frohlich and A. Patra, *Mini-Rev. Org. Chem.*, 2011, **8**, 31; (e) K. Ghosh and I. Saha, *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, 2012, **10**, 9383; (f) D. Zhang, X. Jiang, H. Yang, Z. Su, E. Gao, A. Martinez and G. Gao, *Chem. Commun.*, 2013, **49**, 6149.
- (a) B. Dietrich, T. M. Fyles, J.-M. Lehn, L. G. Pease and D. L. Fyles, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1978, 934; (b) G. Muller, J. Riede and Schmidchen, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 1998, **27**, 1516.
- (a) B. Dietrich, J. Guilhem, J.-M. Lehn, C. Pascard and E. Sonveaux, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1984, **67**; (b) M. Boiocchi, M. Bonizzoni, L. Fabbrizzi, G. Piovani and A. Taglietti, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2003, **125**, 9699.
- A. F. Li, J. H. Wang, F. Wang and Y. B. Jiang, *Chem Soc. Rev.*, 2010, **39**, 3729.
- C. R. Bondy and S. J. Loeb, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2003, **240**, 77.
- (a) J. L. Sessler, N. M. Barkey, G. D. Pantos and V. M. Lynch, *New J. Chem.*, 2007, **31**, 646; (b) C.-L. Chen, Y.-S. Chen, C.-Y. Chen and S.-S. Sun, *Org. Lett.*, 2006, **8**, 5053; (c) O. D. Fox, T. D. Rolls, P. D. Beer and G. B. Drew, *Chem. Commun.*, 2001, 1632; (d) C. B. Reese and H. Yan, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2001, **42**, 5545; (e) C. Denekamp, K. Suwinska, H. Salman, Y. Abraham, Y. Eichen and J. Ben Ari, *Chem.-Eur. J.*, 2007, **13**, 657; (f) M. Renic, N. Basaric and K. Mlinaric-Majerski, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2007, **48**, 7873; (g) M. A. Palacios, R. Nishiyabu, M. Marquez and P. Anzenbacher, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **129**, 7538.
- I. Saha, J. T. Lee and C.-H. Lee, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.* 2015, 3859.
- (a) M. Cametti and K. Rissanen, *Chem. Commun.*, 2009, 2809; (b) M. Cametti and K. Rissanen, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2013, **42**, 2016.
- B. N. G. Giepmans, S. R. Adams, M. H. Ellisman and R. Y. Tsien, *Science*, 2006, **312**, 217; (b) D. W. Domaille, E. L. Que and C. Chang, *J. Nat. Chem. Biol.*, 2008, **4**, 168; (c) L. E. Santos-Figueroa, M. E. Moragues, E. Climent, A. Agostini, R. Martinez-Manez and F. Sancenon, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2013, **42**, 3489.
- X. He, S. Hu, K. Liu, Y. Guo, J. Xu and S. Shao, *Org. Lett.* 2006, **8**, 333.
- L. Wang, X. He, W. Guo, J. Xu and S. Shao, *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, 2011, **9**, 752.
- J. W. Lee, S. Y. Park, B.-K. Cho and J. S. Kim, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2007, **48**, 2541.
- (a) K. Ghosh and G. Masanta, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2006, **47**, 2365; (b) K. Ghosh, G. Masanta, R. Fröhlich, I. D. Petsalakis and G. Theodorakotoulou, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2009, **113**, 7800; (c) K. Ghosh, G. Masanta and A. P. Chattopadhyay, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.*, 2009, **26**, 4515; (d) K. Ghosh, I. Saha, G. Masanta, E. B. Wang and C. A. Parish, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2010, **51**, 343; (e) K. Ghosh and I. Saha, *J. Incl. Phenom. Macrocycl. Chem.*, 2011, **70**, 97; (f) L. Wenfeng, M. Hengchang, L. Con, M. Yuan, Q. Chunxuan, Z. Zhonwei, Y. Zengming, C. Haiying and L. Zqiang, *RSC Adv.*, 2015, **5**, 6869; (g) D. Gu, G. Yang, Y. He, B. Qi, G. Wang, Z. Su, S. Malkondu and S. Erdemir, *Tetrahedron*, 2014, **70**, 5494; (h) D. Gu, G. Yang, Y. He, B. Qi, G. Wang and Z. Su, *Synthetic Metals*, 2009, **159**, 2497; (i) Y. Cui, Q. Chen, D.-D. Zhang, J. Cao and B.-H. Han, *J. Polym. Sci., Part A : Polym. Chem.*, 2010, **48**, 1310; (j) A. K. Mahapatra, G. Hazra, N. K. Das and S. Goswami, *Sens. Actuators (B) : Chem.*, 2011, **156**, 456.
- J. Rokers and T. E. Glass, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2002, **67**, 6113.
- S. Gronert, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 1993, **115**, 10258.